

Recommended citation: Tamás, A., & Koltai, T. (2019). Performance evaluation of university students participating in a simulation game with data envelopment analysis (DEA). In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 1149-1162). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656661.

Performance evaluation of university students participating in a simulation game with data envelopment analysis (DEA)

A Tamás¹

Assistant lecturer, PhD student
Budapest University of Technology and Economics
Faculty of Economics and Social Sciences
Budapest, Hungary

T Koltai

Professor
Budapest University of Technology and Economics
Faculty of Economics and Social Sciences
Budapest, Hungary

Conference Key Areas: New notions of interdisciplinarity in engineering education, New complexity quest in engineering sciences

Keywords: simulation games, performance evaluation, DEA

ABSTRACT

Simulation games have an important role in higher education, because their application allows students to test their theoretical knowledge in a risk free practical environment. The learning by doing concept can also be supported by these methods. Simulation games serve several objectives during the learning process. The multitude of objectives requires sophisticated evaluation methods, which are able to analyse the satisfaction of these targets, and are also able to provide an aggregate performance measure for grading purposes. Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is able to consider several aspect of simulation game results using sound mathematical methodology which increases the objectivity of the evaluation. Applying DEA for the evaluation of student's performance in a simulation game is a novel area of DEA application. This paper shows how an input oriented constant returns to scale radial model can be used to evaluate the results of student groups in a production simulation game. The paper presents the applied mathematical model, the application environment and summarises the main benefits of this new evaluation tool for grading and assessment purposes.

¹ Corresponding Author
Alexandra TAMÁS
tamasa@mvt.bme.hu

1 INTRODUCTION

The application of simulation games in higher education has become increasingly popular through the last decades. Several studies show that the use of simulation games in engineering education leads to positive attitude towards the subject in which these games are applied and that they present an effective alternative to traditional teaching methods. A large number of papers analyses the impact of simulation games on the participating student and applies various methods for the evaluation of the development of the participants.

In this paper, Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is applied for the performance evaluation of student groups in a simulation game. First, the paper reviews the role and application possibilities of simulation games in engineering education. Next, DEA as a method for the evaluation of the results of a simulation game is discussed. The basic concepts of DEA are introduced and the application environment of the presented research is outlined. The production simulation game (Factory Midi from EcoSim) used in the operations management master program of the Budapest University of Technology and Economics is presented and the DEA models proposed for the evaluation of the results of the participating students are explained. Finally, the use of the outcome of the game for course evaluation and the potential insights of the learning process during the game are presented.

2 THE ROLE OF SIMULATION GAMES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Simulation games embody a new teaching methodology with the aim of helping students to increase their comprehension of course subjects. Used as a pedagogical tool, simulation games complement traditional educational methods and contribute to integrating complex knowledge obtained from different disciplines by following the “learning by doing” philosophy. There is plenty of research dealing with exploring the potential advantages of this method. ([9], [13]) Games can be applied effectively to engage students, motivate them and give them a chance to create a link between theory and real-world problems. [1] They can serve as a method of organized experiential learning, moreover, they may include the element of fun. [8] The chance for immediate feedback helps students to experiment the possible effects of strategy planning and decision making in a risk-free environment, and without real pressure on them. [17]

Among others, Deshpande and Huang [8] surveyed the existing applications of simulation games in engineering education. They collected several simulation game examples reviewing the literature and grouped explored practice according to professional fields. They found evidence of a large amount of applied games in civil, electrical, mechanical, environmental and chemical engineering education. A systematic survey of simulation games used in software engineering education was conducted by Caulfield et al. [3]. Both studies concluded that a large number of games have been developed and used and that as a pedagogical device they are becoming more and more popular in higher education.

For the illustration of the role of simulation games in engineering education, we have collected four application examples at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics.

- Professors of the electric power system laboratory in the Electrical Engineering master's degree program developed an educational framework for the interactive simulation of power exchanges. In the simulation game, participating students play the roles as power plant owners on a single market and they have to compete with each other. The aim of the instructors was to highlight the problems and challenges of the power exchange market and to encourage competition between students to provide an atmosphere similar to the real-world environment. [15]
- In a simulation game used in the Chemical Engineering program, students have to work in groups and plan how to convert the recipe of a specified molecule from laboratory to industrial scale. Besides chemical engineering knowledge, resource planning, time scheduling and the ability of working in a team is also developed during the game.
- The Department of Transport Technology and Economics applies a supply chain simulation game in which students can test their knowledge in a virtual environment as members (manufacturer, supplier or retailer) of the supply chain. Students, acting as companies, have to acquire, stock, produce, distribute and transport multiple products. The main results of the game are that students realized some possible pitfalls in the operation of the supply chains, became familiar with the practical use of the methods learned in theory, practiced presentation techniques and reasoning, furthermore, developed their ability to react quickly under decision making pressure. [2]
- A simulation game is also used in the Service Marketing module of the economic master degree program. During the game, student groups take over the leadership of a virtual hotel and the associated ski centre. Students need to plan a strategy, analyse data and make decisions in order to maintain the hotel's effective operation. With the help of the simulation game, students are able to synthesize knowledge acquired from different subjects related to service management and marketing management and they gain a virtual leadership experience as well.

We have shown that simulation games are widely used in many fields of higher education and they present an effective alternative or supplement to traditional teaching methods. In line with the fact that simulation games provide students with an instant feedback on their performance, in the rest of the study, a new method of the assessment of student's performance will be discussed. The following chapters present how Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), a mathematical-based decision support tool, can be an appropriate method for the evaluation of students participating in a simulation game.

3 THE BASIC CONCEPTS OF DEA

Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) is a linear programming model that has been applied to measure efficiency in various areas. The method attracted global attention after Charnes et al. [5] published their paper, which first introduced the term DEA. Since then, a number of research has been presented concerning the application of DEA for performance evaluation in financial sector institutions ([16], [18]), in hospitals and in related health services organizations ([7], [10]), of different types of transportation systems ([4], [14]) and it is widely used in the field of education as well ([11], [6]).

DEA measures the efficiency of a production or service system relative to the best performing ones (called peers). The performance measure is the ratio of the weighted output and the weighted input but weights are determined with the help of sound mathematical models. The production or service systems analysed with DEA are called decision making units (DMUs), because they can independently decide on the amount of inputs used. The inputs and outputs applied in the evaluation should be selected properly to express the performance of DMUs adequately. The outputs are such operational results that are important for the decision maker, and thus for evaluation, and DMUs have to make decisions on the amount of resources used to generate them. In stores, for example, the volume of sales, the satisfaction level of customers, the speed of service or the increase in store turnover can be outputs. Inputs may refer to any resource that the management considers to be important and the amount used of them is a determining factor in the evaluation. In a store, mentioned in our example, the number of employees, the size of the shop floor or the logistics equipment and the service personnel carrying out the delivery of the products can be inputs.

The comparison of the DMUs is based on the weighted amount of outputs and the weighted amount of inputs. Weighting is determined by exact mathematical tools based on the characteristics of the DMUs. The ratio of weighted inputs to weighted outputs can be calculated in two ways. If the purpose of the management is to maintain the current value of the outputs but using less inputs, then the sum of the weighted outputs is divided by the sum of the weighted inputs when calculating the value of efficiency. This case is called input oriented approach. If the aim of the management is to produce as much output as possible with the available amount of the inputs, then the sum of the weighted inputs is divided by the sum of the weighted outputs. This is called output oriented approach.

DEA empirically identifies the efficient frontier of a set of DMUs based on the input and output variables. The result is an efficiency score for every DMU, which reflects the rate by which a given DMU could improve its productivity relative to its peers. The highest value of the efficiency score is equal to 1 and the lowest value is equal to 0. It is important to emphasize that the analysed DMUs are only effective or ineffective relative to each other. Based on the data (inputs and outputs) of a specific set of

organizational units we conclude that a DMU works well or not. However, this does not mean that theoretically it is not possible to achieve higher performance.

One of the greatest benefits of DEA that it can take into account a number of factors while evaluating performance. Factors, which are measured in different scales (for example net profit, customer satisfaction, speed of delivery) can be aggregated with the help of the weights. This benefit provides the chance to use DEA in many different fields of performance evaluation. A special such application area is the evaluation of students participating in an educational purpose simulation game.

4 EVALUATING SIMULATION GAME RESULTS USING DEA

4.1 Application environment

To apply DEA for evaluating the results of simulation games is a new and promising area. In the simulation game used in this research, student groups form the DMUs, and their relative performance is evaluated. The production simulation game applied in this paper was developed by EcoSim Ltd. to support production management education. The game is used in the *Decision Making in Production and Service Systems* course of the Production and Operations Management Master's degree program at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics. During this program, students have to acquire different skills from different areas of management. Although we used this simulation game to measure the overall production management knowledge of students, decision making required marketing, financial and accounting skills as well. Thus, we evaluate the application efficiency of production, financial and marketing knowledge obtained in the master program as well.

The objective of the game is to simulate production management decision making in a car engine manufacturing factory. The factory produces three different car engines for five different markets in seven consecutive periods. Each market has its own demand characteristics. Car engines are assembled from parts on assembly lines operated by workers. Decisions must be made by each student group for the next production period in the following areas: sales and marketing, production, investment and financial decisions. The simulation program generates the results of the actual production period. Students get a production report and a financial report based on which each student group tries to increase operational performance of the next periods.

Two outputs, cumulated production quantity and net cumulated profit, and four inputs were applied in the analysis: cumulated number of workers, cumulated number of machine hours, cumulated sum of money spent on raw materials, cumulated value of credit.

4.2 DEA models used in the analysis

The study used two input oriented DEA models for the evaluation of student group performance at the end of the 7th period. We assumed constant returns to scale (CRS) relationship between the input and the output values, that is, the size of the input does

not influence the marginal change of the output. In the first case, a CRS model was applied without any restrictions. In the second case, a CRS model with weight restrictions (CRS-AR) was used.

The mathematical formulation of the applied DEA model is based on the maximization of the ratio of weighted outputs and weighted inputs. This ratio is the efficiency score. The weights are the variables of the model, and for each student group the best possible weights are looked for. It is assumed, however, that these best possible weights are used by each student group and the ratio of weighted outputs and weighted inputs must be less than 1. If the best possible weights are found for a student group (for the reference group) and it is equal to 1, then the group is considered efficient. If the efficiency score is less than 1, then the car engine production process operated by the student group is inefficient and the sources of inefficient operation can be explored with the help of DEA.

Table 1. List of notations

<i>Indices:</i>	
j	- index of decision making units (DMUs), $j = 1, \dots, J$
i	- index of inputs, $i = 1, \dots, I$
k	- index of outputs, $k = 1, \dots, K$
z	- <i>running index of weights</i>
R	- index of the reference DMU
<i>Parameters:</i>	
J	- number of DMUs,
I	- number of inputs,
K	- number of outputs,
x_{ij}	- quantity of input i of DMU j ,
y_{kj}	- quantity of output k of DMU j ,
$L_{z,i}^{INP}$	- lower limit of the ratio of input weights z and i ,
$L_{z,k}^{OUT}$	- lower limit of the ratio of output weights z and k ,
$U_{z,i}^{INP}$	- upper limit of the ratio of input weights z and i ,
$U_{z,k}^{OUT}$	- upper limit of the ratio of output weights z and k ,
<i>Variables:</i>	
u_i	- weight of input i ,
v_k	- weight of output k .

Let us assume that J number of DMUs (student groups) are to be evaluated, when K different outputs are observed and I different inputs are used. Notations used in this paper are listed in *Table 1*. We would like to determine the best possible weights for DMU R . If y_{kj} are the observed output values of output k , and x_{ij} are the observed input values of input i for DMU j , furthermore v_k and u_i denote the output and input weights, then the linear programming formulation for finding the most favourable weights for the evaluation of DMU R is as follows,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Max} \left(\sum_{k=1}^K v_k y_{kR} / \sum_{i=1}^I u_i x_{iR} \right) \\
 & \sum_{k=1}^K v_k y_{kj} / \sum_{i=1}^I u_i x_{ij} \leq 1 \quad j = 1, \dots, J \\
 & u_i, v_k \geq 0 \quad i = 1, \dots, I; \quad k = 1, \dots, K
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

If problem (1) is transformed to eliminate the ratio of variables, and the weighted input is fixed (equal to 1) in order to get unique solution for LP problem (1), then the primal version of the input oriented, constant return to scale model is obtained,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Max} \left(\sum_{k=1}^K v_k y_{kR} \right) \\
 & \sum_{i=1}^I u_i x_{iR} = 1 \\
 & \sum_{k=1}^K v_k y_{kj} - \sum_{i=1}^I u_i x_{ij} \leq 0 \quad j = 1, \dots, J \\
 & u_i, v_k \geq 0 \quad i = 1, \dots, I; \quad k = 1, \dots, K
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

In primal model (2), the optimal value of the weights of inputs and outputs are determined by linear programming. Model (2) must be solved for each DMU, that is, at each solution of the model the reference DMU changes. The results are the optimal weights and the efficiency scores of the DMUs.

Frequently, the value of some weights is zero, that is, when the efficiency score is calculated, some inputs and outputs have zero weight. Inputs and outputs with zero weight are ignored in the evaluation, which is not always acceptable for evaluation purposes. To avoid the problem of zero weight, restrictions can be added to model (2). One possible form of weight restriction is when constraints for all possible pairs of inputs and outputs are given,

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{k,z}^{(OUT)} & \leq \frac{v_z}{v_k} \leq U_{k,z}^{(OUT)} \quad k = 1, \dots, K; \quad z = 1, \dots, K; \quad k \neq z \\
 L_{i,z}^{(INP)} & \leq \frac{u_z}{u_i} \leq U_{i,z}^{(INP)} \quad i = 1, \dots, I; \quad z = 1, \dots, I; \quad i \neq z
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Model (2) is referenced in this paper as the input oriented CRS model and Model (2) completed with constraints (3) are referenced in the model as the input oriented CRS-AR (Assurance Region) model.

Weight restrictions are introduced in order to prevent the inputs or outputs from being over-emphasised or ignored in the analysis. In our case the ratio of output weights was 0.25, that is, the role of an output has always at least 25% role in the evaluation. The ratio of input weight pairs was 0.1.

4.3 Comparison of the performance of student groups

In this paper we analysed data produced by 19 student groups (DMUs). We assessed their performance based on the aggregate data of seven decision making periods. *Table 2.* and *Figure 1.* shows the results of the student groups according to the two DEA models. The table shows the efficiency scores calculated on the basis of the two models, while the diagram illustrates the efficiency changes of the DMUs.

Table 2. Efficiency scores

DMU	CRS %	CRS-AR %
1	98,25	82,51
2	89,94	79,28
3	98,59	86,07
4	100	100
5	93,80	84,53
6	100	99,09
7	100	100
8	86,28	76,27
9	100	97,74
10	100	95,11
11	100	90,00
12	86,53	75,14
13	87,12	72,78
14	98,41	83,06
15	100	99,70
16	96,71	81,12
17	87,29	55,72
18	91,11	78,50
19	100	96,82

Figure 1. Relative efficiency diagram

The simple CRS model provided eight efficient groups. It means that these teams performed the best during the game, the other eleven groups resulted inefficient. Best performing groups, acting as potential peers, provide the opportunity for inefficient ones to benchmark their activities. For example, the efficiency score of group number 8 indicates that this group achieved an 86,28% performance relative to the best

performing teams, that is, it could increase its performance by taking similar steps as its peers. This model shows a relatively balanced competition between the groups, each achieving over 85% performance.

Nevertheless, this balanced trend cannot be observed when using the CRS-AR model. In order to evaluate the performance of the teams without 0 weight on any input or output, we introduced weight restrictions into the model. As a result, none of the factors received too high or too low attention in the analysis, thus, all inputs and outputs were included in each team's performance evaluation. Out of the eight efficient groups from above only two groups (number 4 and 7) remained efficient. In addition, we can notice some relevant set-backs (~15-16%) in the case of groups number 1, 13, 14 and 16, and a huge one (~32%) in the case of group 17. To explain the differences observed between the efficiency scores of the two models we have to examine the basic input and output data and the weights assigned for them (see *Appendix*).

In the example of group 17, it can be seen that while the CRS model yielded an efficiency score above 87%, the CRS-AR model reduced it to almost 55%. Examining the weight data shows that the CRS model assigned weights to only one input and one output, and as a result, the weaker factors were not evaluated in the model. Group 17 produced the lowest net profit of all and used the highest amount of credit. The CRS-AR model put weights on these factors, which significantly reduced its efficiency. The simple CRS model ignored the outlier input and output values with a value of 0 or low weight. The CRS-AR model modified the efficiency data taking into account all factors by weight restrictions.

Table 3. Final results

DMU	Efficiency (%)	Score (points)
1	82,51	21
2	79,28	20
3	86,07	22
4	100	25
5	84,53	22
6	99,09	25
7	100	25
8	76,27	20
9	97,74	24
10	95,11	24
11	90,00	23
12	75,14	19
13	72,78	19
14	83,06	21
15	99,70	25
16	81,12	21
17	55,72	15
18	78,50	20
19	96,82	24

In order to evaluate students' performance equally, the results generated by the CRS-AR model were taken into account in the final evaluation. Efficiency scores were converted into a score, which is a factor in determining the final grade. Based on the relative efficiencies of the CRS-AR model, scores (or points) were assigned to each student group according to *Table 3*. The maximum available score was 25 points; the minimum was 15. The 10 points between the minimum and maximum value was assigned to students based on a linear transformation of the efficiency scores. The results obtainable from the simulation game represented 25% of the final grade of the course.

5 CONCLUSION

Simulation games have an important role in higher education, because students can test their theoretical knowledge in a risk free practical environment. The learning by doing concept can also be supported by these methods.

This paper listed several examples of the application of simulation games in engineering and management education. To evaluate the performance of participants in these games on an objective way is not easy as a consequence of the several objectives of the learning process. Data Envelopment Analysis is an appropriate tool for considering several evaluation criteria at the same time and for providing an aggregate measure of performance.

The application of two DEA models was presented in this paper to show how the results of a production simulation game can be evaluated. A traditional input oriented radial model was applied first. The results, however, did not contain several evaluation objectives as a consequence of the zero weights found in the results. The application of weight restriction in the assurance region model eliminated this problem and provided a model which expresses better the teaching objectives. The generated efficiency score was directly transformed into grading categories.

The presented application showed that DEA can really be applied for the performance evaluation of students in a simulation game. The analysis of the results demonstrated that careful model selection is required. DEA is based on linear programming, consequently, it is an objective evaluation tool. There are, however, subjective elements of the evaluation as well. The instructor must decide on the important elements of the evaluation process. This subjective element can be influenced by model selection and by the careful parameter setting of the selected models.

The result of DEA is not exclusively the efficiency score, although it is the most important for grading purposes. Additional DEA results, such as the groups of peers, the slack values and the change of efficiency score over time can provide further insights into the learning process (see for example [12]). To explore all the possibilities of DEA in this new area is a topic of our further research.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ben-Zvi, T. (2010). The efficacy of business simulation games in creating Decision Support Systems: An experimental investigation. *Decision Support Systems*, 49(1), 61-69.
- [2] Bóna, K., Kovács, G., & Lénárt, B. (2009). Egy ellátási lánc szimulációs játék (SCSG) modellje és az egyetemi oktatásban végrehajtott tesztelés gyakorlati tapasztalatai. *Innováció és Fenntartható Felszíni Közlekedés Konferencia*, 2-4.
- [3] Caulfield, C., Xia, J. C., Veal, D., & Maj, S. (2011). A systematic survey of games used for software engineering education. *Modern Applied Science*, 5(6), 28-43.
- [4] Chang, Y. T., Zhang, N., Danao, D., & Zhang, N. (2013). Environmental efficiency analysis of transportation system in China: A non-radial DEA approach. *Energy policy*, 58, 277-283.
- [5] Charnes, A., Cooper, W. W., & Rhodes, E. (1978). Measuring the efficiency of decision making units. *European journal of operational research*, 2(6), 429-444.
- [6] Colbert, A., Levary, R. R., & Shaner, M. C. (2000). Determining the relative efficiency of MBA programs using DEA. *European journal of operational research*, 125(3), 656-669.
- [7] Dénes, R. V., Kecskés, J., Koltai, T., & Dénes, Z. (2017). The Application of Data Envelopment Analysis in Healthcare Performance Evaluation of Rehabilitation Departments in Hungary. *Quality Innovation Prosperity*, 21(3), 127-142.
- [8] Deshpande, A. A., & Huang, S. H. (2011). Simulation games in engineering education: A state-of-the-art review. *Computer applications in engineering education*, 19(3), 399-410.
- [9] Ekaterina, G., Anastasya, B., & Ksenya, G. (2015). Sociocultural competence training in higher engineering education: the role of gaming simulation. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 166, 339-343.
- [10] Hofmarcher, M. M., Paterson, I., & Riedel, M. (2002). Measuring hospital efficiency in Austria—a DEA approach. *Health Care Management Science*, 5(1), 7-14.

- [11] Johnes, J. (2006). Data envelopment analysis and its application to the measurement of efficiency in higher education. *Economics of education review*, 25(3), 273-288.
- [12] Koltai, T., Lozano, S., Uzonyi-Kecskés, J., Moreno, P. (2017). Evaluation of the results of a production simulation game using a dynamic DEA approach. *Computers and Industrial Engineering*, 105, 1-11.
- [13] Lean, J., Moizer, J., Towler, M., & Abbey, C. (2006). Simulations and games: Use and barriers in higher education. *Active learning in higher education*, 7(3), 227-242.
- [14] Martín, J. C., & Roman, C. (2001). An application of DEA to measure the efficiency of Spanish airports prior to privatization. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 7(3), 149-157.
- [15] Sleisz, Á. (2013). Power exchange simulation as an interactive educational tool. In *2013 4th International Youth Conference on Energy (IYCE)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [16] Staub, R. B., Souza, G. D. S., & Tabak, B. M. (2010). Evolution of bank efficiency in Brazil: A DEA approach. *European journal of operational research*, 202(1), 204-213.
- [17] Tiwari, S. R., Nafees, L., & Krishnan, O. (2014). Simulation as a pedagogical tool: Measurement of impact on perceived effective learning. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 12(3), 260-270.
- [18] Wu, D. D., Yang, Z., & Liang, L. (2006). Using DEA-neural network approach to evaluate branch efficiency of a large Canadian bank. *Expert systems with applications*, 31(1), 108-115.

APPENDIX

1. Data sheet

DMU	Production quantity	Net profit	Workers	Machine hours	Raw materials	Credit
1	2 988 000	215 200	13 541	2 927 300	5 980 100	2 973 800
2	2 417 100	78 500	10 861	3 005 900	5 076 500	2 258 700
3	3 054 100	756 100	16 265	2 895 800	6 189 500	1 500 000
4	2 757 300	1 961 200	11 747	2 848 500	4 565 000	805 300
5	2 660 900	478 200	11 680	3 066 700	5 416 400	2 025 700
6	2 316 400	1 240 000	10 541	2 594 800	4 524 500	444 600
7	2 809 000	1 711 500	12 166	2 790 200	4 899 200	714 100
8	2 109 500	268 900	10 241	2 717 100	4 195 100	1 138 200
9	3 002 200	1 231 500	12 039	3 505 300	4 713 500	2 885 700
10	3 090 700	870 700	12 229	3 545 500	5 519 400	3 266 500
11	2 466 900	570 600	10 375	2 738 100	4 827 500	906 000
12	2 329 200	120 900	12 791	2 542 700	5 003 500	870 700
13	2 453 400	-59 200	13 341	2 632 500	4 982 200	2 399 200
14	2 621 500	-375 800	10 540	3 423 400	5 739 100	3 213 600
15	3 050 400	1 511 800	13 916	2 851 500	4 833 200	1 029 000
16	2 911 000	184 500	15 521	2 813 900	5 789 700	1 739 400
17	2 112 600	-1 347 500	12 750	2 262 300	4 945 300	4 431 300
18	2 838 500	236 000	13 681	3 046 900	5 920 300	1 757 600
19	3 056 600	1 650 900	14 343	2 971 600	4 799 800	3 586 300

2. Weight values in the simple CRS model

DMU	Production quantity	Net profit	Workers	Machine hours	Raw materials	Credit
1	0,3288	0	0,0398	0,1573	0	0
2	0,3721	0	0,0783	0,0296	0	0,0267
3	0,3228	0	0	0,3453	0	0
4	0,3571	0,0078	0,0561	0,1198	0	0
5	0,3525	0	0,0522	0,1271	0	0
6	0,4317	0	0,0826	0	0	0,2911
7	0,356	0	0,0431	0,1703	0	0
8	0,409	0	0,0906	0	0,0077	0,0349
9	0,3331	0	0,0461	0,099	0,0208	0
10	0,3236	0	0,0479	0,1167	0	0
11	0,4054	0	0,0853	0,0322	0	0,0291
12	0,3715	0	0	0,3169	0	0,2231
13	0,3551	0	0	0,3799	0	0
14	0,3754	0	0,0949	0	0	0
15	0,3278	0	0,0397	0,1568	0	0
16	0,3322	0	0	0,3554	0	0
17	0,4132	0	0	0,442	0	0
18	0,321	0	0,0389	0,1535	0	0
19	0,3072	0,0369	0,0171	0,0354	0,1353	0

3. Weight values in CRS-AR model

DMU	Production quantity	Net profit	Workers	Machine hours	Raw materials	Credit
1	0,2712	0,0678	0,0193	0,1932	0,0193	0,0193
2	0,3254	0,0813	0,0841	0,0084	0,0084	0,0084
3	0,2654	0,0663	0,0189	0,189	0,0189	0,0189
4	0,3079	0,077	0,0219	0,2193	0,0219	0,0219
5	0,304	0,076	0,0785	0,0079	0,0079	0,0079
6	0,3773	0,0943	0,0452	0,0452	0,0452	0,4524
7	0,3089	0,0772	0,021	0,2104	0,021	0,0756
8	0,3504	0,0876	0,0905	0,0091	0,0091	0,0091
9	0,2953	0,0738	0,0575	0,0057	0,0575	0,0057
10	0,2875	0,0719	0,0743	0,0074	0,0074	0,0074
11	0,3449	0,0862	0,0891	0,0089	0,0089	0,0089
12	0,3185	0,0796	0,0227	0,2268	0,0227	0,0227
13	0,2985	0,0746	0,0213	0,2126	0,0213	0,0213
14	0,3286	0,0822	0,0849	0,0085	0,0085	0,0085
15	0,2908	0,0727	0,0109	0,1089	0,1089	0,0109
16	0,2743	0,0686	0,0195	0,1954	0,0195	0,0195
17	0,3138	0,0784	0,0223	0,2235	0,0223	0,0223
18	0,2709	0,0677	0,0193	0,1929	0,0193	0,0193
19	0,2791	0,0698	0,0105	0,1046	0,1046	0,0105